

CLEWs-Based Prediction of Zambia's Trajectory to Net-Zero

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Executive Summary

This study aimed at predicting the possible outcomes of two policy measures being implemented in Zambia, namely: (i) increased renewable energy and (ii) scaled-up crop irrigation. This study applied a model-based analysis approach, CLEWs framework, using the OSeMOSYS tool to build and run scenarios for analysis and understand the nexus between climate, land, energy and water systems.

Based on the findings of this study, it is evident that, owing to the interplay between energy, water, land and climate, implementation of policies in one sector would affect the demand, cost and emission profile in other sectors. On this basis, the study recommends that policy-makers embrace the use of models to foster evidence-based planning and decision-making.

1. Introduction

Zambia has embarked on a developmental pathway aimed at becoming a prosperous middle-income country by the year 2030 underpinned by socio-economic growth and environmental sustainability. This has been amidst several challenges including adverse effects of climate change, particularly extended droughts. The United Nations Office for Disaster Risk Reduction (2021) noted that extended droughts would negatively impact the performance of key sectors, leading to high risk of energy, water and food insecurity.

Zambia has put in place policies and strategies to address climate change and targets to reduce up to 38Gg CO₂eq (47%) by 2030 (and attain net-zero by 2070) while also seeking to increase its sector-wide adaptive capacity and resilience to effects of climate change (Government of Zambia, 2021). Some notable policies that Zambia is implementing seek to:

1. Enhance food security by upscaling irrigation-based crop production; and

2. Increased the share of renewable energy in the national energy mix to 10%.

This study seeks to predict the outcomes of these policy measures and assess their implications in relation to the interplay between energy, water, land and climate. The main aim is to understand how their implementation alters the demand, cost and emission profile in other sectors. This is key in providing insights and recommendations to inform policy-making and integrated planning for Zambia.

2. Methodology

This study applied a model-based analysis approach, the Climate, Land, Energy, and Water Systems (CLEWs) framework, using the OSeMOSYS tool – an open source energy modelling system. The tool allows for flexibility and functionality to perform integrated analysis in CLEWs framework which permits investigation of the interactions and interdependencies among climate, land, energy, and water systems, to expedite research-based decision-making (Ramos et al., 2022).

Zambia’s reference energy system (RES) was modelled as the baseline model (see figure 1). The RES included commodities and technologies relating to energy, land and water resources. The data used to build the RES was primarily drawn from the starter data kit (SAND) provided within the OSeMOSYS toolkit. The data on energy demand and supply was sourced from the energy balance and energy sector reports for Zambia. Further, data relating to agriculture and water data was obtained from the Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO), Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD), and International Energy Agency (IEA) databases.

Figure 1: Reference CLEWs Diagram for Zambia

The study considered three scenarios, namely: (i) the business of usual (BAU); (ii) Increased share of renewable energy resources (ISRE) in energy mix; and (iii)

Increased agricultural productivity through irrigation (IAPI). The BAU scenario represented a state of no policy implementation or resource constraints. The ISRE scenario depicted a situation where the country deploys at least 100MW of on-grid solar annually over the entire time series. It assumed that the country had enough grid capacity to uptake variable power. This IAPI scenario reflected increased investment in the irrigation system by doubling the land size used for irrigated maize production in 2024 and projected based on demand growth.

3. Results

The study endeavoured to understand the interplay between the climate, land, energy and water systems, based on the model predictions. The results would be analysed in more detail by considering the following key focus areas:

3.1. How does increased share of renewable energy affect Zambia’s trajectory to net-zero?

The results revealed some useful insights on comparative terms of the BAU and ISRE scenarios. As shown in figure 2, the model picks, in BAU scenario, that Zambia’s installed capacity exceeds the country’s electricity demand and proposes a switch in investment focus from hydro power generation to other sources of energy, notably coal, biomass, geothermal, wind and solar. The results of the ISRE scenario suggest a further displacement of hydro and a share of coal when additional solar is introduced.

Figure 2: Modelled Electricity Generation Capacity for Zambia

In terms of the investment profile, results indicate an increase in total capital investment. However, this increase would be regarded as a trade-off on greenhouse gas (GHGs) abatement on account of reduced consumption of coal.

Figure 3: Capital Investment Cost based on ISRE Scenario

3.2. How does upscaling irrigation system production affect other sectors in Zambia?

Zambia's maize production depends largely on rain-fed agriculture. A comparative view of the BAU and IAPI scenarios, see figure 4, forecast that an increase in the scale of irrigation for maize production would increase annual yields for the crop. This is true if the total land under cultivation is held constant. The results also entail that, for the same production scale, the land requirement for crop production could be reduced in the irrigation system compared to rain-fed agriculture.

Figure 4: Crop production based on IAPI Scenario

On the other hand, the model indicated that water demand for agriculture increased in the IAPI scenario and so was the energy demand for irrigation. Figure 5 shows variability in water demand with significant increase in agriculture and power sectors. This can be linked to growth in the need for water for irrigation and water usage in thermal power generation. Increase in water requirement in power generation is induced by increased demand for energy in the agriculture sector. In Zambia, this entails increased competition for water among various sectors water-users including energy, public and industries.

Figure 5: Water Demand based on IAPI Scenario

Furthermore, as shown in figure 6, the model depicted a notable increase in GHG emissions in the IAPI scenario against the BAU scenario. The increase can be associated with the growth in energy demand which introduced additional consumption in the energy mix.

Figure 6: Emission Profile based IAPI Scenario

4. Discussion

The model results suggest limited investment in hydro in preference for other energy resources for electricity generation. Zambia relies largely on hydro for electricity generation. The country has an on-grid installed capacity of 3.8 GW. Approximately 84% of this capacity is hydro while coal takes up 9%, HFO represents 3%, 2% comes from diesel and 2% from solar (Energy Regulation Board, 2022, p. 37). With a peak demand of around 2.4GW, Zambia has sufficient capacity at generation. However, this is rarely the case given the country’s vulnerability to extended droughts. In the medium to long-term, the country would need to diversify its energy mix by introducing energy resources that are less susceptible to climate change. This agrees with the model prediction.

Notably, the BAU scenario picked coal and biomass as candidate technologies for electricity generation. This presents itself as a drift away from the desired path to attainment of the country’s emission reduction targets. Its bearing is lessened by introduction of solar in the ISRE scenario despite the increase in capital investment cost. Analysis of the IAPI scenario portrays a similar pathway. Increased irrigation pushed for increase in water pumping demand leading to growth in energy requirement and subsequently production of more GHG emissions. This presents a trade-off between higher crop yield for lesser land requirement against increased investment in electricity generation and higher emissions. In this scenario, the country

may decide to change the excess agricultural land to forest to create a sink for GHG emissions.

To arrive at such decisions, it would be helpful to undertake further analysis using the CLEWs approach to achieve an all-inclusive integrated resource planning. This would assure a holistic analysis that extends beyond climate considerations to encompass the integration of energy, land and water systems (Covre, 2024). The use of models in predicting, analysing and considering the nexus between various natural resources has the power to usher in efficiency and sustainability in resource utilisation. It also promotes practicality scrutinising the feasibility and cost-effectiveness of all considered measures to spur informed decision-making.

5. Conclusion

This study has predicted the possible outcomes of two policy measures being implemented in Zambia, increased renewable energy and scaled-up crop irrigation. Based on the assessment of the interplay between energy, water, land and climate, the study has shown that implementation of policies in one sector would affect the demand, cost and emission profile in other sectors. On this basis, the study recommends that policy-makers embrace the use of models to foster evidence-based planning.

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